

IoT-Powered Weight Sensing and Garbage Monitoring Systems

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Abstract: Maintaining the cleanliness of the city has always required the hard work of those who work on the bottom floor, emptying the trash cans when they are full. The occurrence of a rubbish bin filling up is not entirely based on a time pattern; rather, it can occasionally fill up quickly or take longer than usual. One creative approach to improving the efficiency and smoothness of this procedure is IOT Garbage Monitoring using Weight Sensing Paper. Furthermore, weight sensors are affixed beneath the trash cans. Therefore, the system transmits the weight of the rubbish bins' fill as well as their degree of fill over the internet. The benefit of this combination sensing is that the authorities can also determine the weight of the rubbish bin. The vehicles can be driven straight to the waste bin for evacuation if it is not yet full but the weight of the fill has surpassed the capacity of the garbage lifting vehicles.

Keywords: IOT trash, paper sensing, weight lifting, and vehicle lifting

I. Introduction

Solid waste management, which affects our society's ecology and health, has been one of the biggest environmental challenges. One of the main issues of the modern era is the identification, monitoring, and management of trash. Keeping an eye on the rubbish in trash cans by hand is a laborious task that takes more time, money, and human labor than is possible with today's technology. This approach uses automation to manage waste. This IOT garbage monitoring system is a creative method to maintain healthy and clean towns. Hazardous pollution and its ensuing consequences on human health, concerning global warming and ozone layer depletion, etc., could be threats to this. The majority of environmental pollution may be caused by municipal solid waste.

For the created municipal solid waste to be removed effectively and efficiently, proper maintenance becomes essential. It is believed that because of the dustbin's inconsistent garbage pickup, the waste area frequently becomes overly crowded. This article suggests an e-monitoring system that integrates Wi-Fi-based software and an embedded system with Internet of Things technologies. It would be possible to efficiently monitor the waste collection status using the projected system. This design specifies a method that would stop the bin from overflowing unintentionally by allowing the garbage level to be checked often. Furthermore, it has the ability to notify the appropriate authority to clean up in the event of spills. The ultrasonic sensor may detect and track the dust bin's initial level height. The Arduino UNO is programmed such that an information message asking a clean-up is delivered as soon as a specific filling level or weight is detected.

II. Block Diagram and Working

The IOT garbage monitoring system described in this paper is a really creative technology that will contribute to the cleanliness of cities. Through Wi-Fi, this system keeps an eye on the trash cans and notifies the municipality department's Android device of the amount of trash that has been gathered in them.

The system detects the rubbish level and compares it with the garbage bins' level using ultrasonic sensors that are positioned over the bins. The system uses an LCD screen, a Wi-Fi modem, an AVR family microcontroller, and a buzzer to acknowledge receipt of data if needed. The weight of the bins and the amount of trash collected are shown on the LCD panel. The weight and garbage level status are displayed on the LCD panel. By using the Android development platform and IOT (Wi-Fi) to provide the garbage bin's status, this system helps to maintain the city clean by providing information on the rubbish levels in the bins.

Figure 1: Block Diagram for Garbage Monitoring using IoT

III. Results and Conclusion

A demo unit is constructed, and the paper work titled " Weight-sensing IOT-based waste monitoring" is successfully created and built. The outcomes are deemed satisfactory.

Figure 2: Circuit connection for Garbage monitoring on printed circuit board

Since it is a demo module and the LCD panel is used to display the amount of trash in the bin, we have just looked at one waste bin. However, when the system is put to use for real-world reasons, it is possible to track the trash cans in each neighborhood. An integrated Wi-Fi modem (IOT) and ultrasonic sensor system for efficient and cost-effective rubbish collection is shown in this study. The developed system provides improved databases for waste quantity and garbage pickup time at each location. We looked at the current solutions for IOT deployment. By implementing this paper, we will stop excessive garbage from pouring out of containers in residential areas that were previously loaded manually or with the help of loaders in traditional vehicles. It is capable to interact with the collection truck and automatically check the garbage level. The recommended system's technology is adequate to ensure that it is perfect for overseeing and controlling the solid waste collection procedure in an environmentally friendly setting.

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